

Investigating sensory dominance in product experience

Hendrik N.J. Schifferstein* and Anna Fenko **

* *Department of Industrial Design, Delft University of Technology, Delft, the Netherlands,
h.n.j.schifferstein@tudelft.nl*

** *Department of Industrial Design, Delft University of Technology, Delft, the Netherlands, a.b.fenko@tudelft.nl*

Abstract: Although all senses are open to obtain information during user-product interactions, some sensory information can have a larger effect on the product experience than other. In this paper, we present an overview of studies we performed to investigate the importance of the sensory modalities during user-product interactions. Some studies have used a questionnaire approach, in which we asked participants to evaluate their past experiences with particular products either in general, or at specific moments in time. In other studies, we have used an experimental approach to quantify the relative contribution of the different senses. In addition, we highlight the role of language and culture.

Key words: *multisensory; dominance; sensory integration; importance; product design; product experience.*

1. Introduction

From an ecological point of view, the task of the perceptual systems is to obtain useful information about the environment. When people interact with products, all their senses are used to obtain information [1]. When a person uses a durable consumer product, sensory feedback is used directly to operate the product [e.g., 2]. For instance, a person who uses a vacuum cleaner can judge on the basis of what he sees (the carpet becomes clean) and hears (tickling of pieces of dirt in the nozzle) whether he has to clean the current section again, or whether he can continue with another section. As a consequence, designers tend to involve an increasing number of sensory modalities for playing functional roles in user-product interactions, such as in improving the usability of software interfaces [e.g., 3] or in making complex virtual data sets accessible [e.g., 4].

Furthermore, sensory inputs affect the way in which people experience and evaluate products. For instance, the noisy sound of the motor suggests that the vacuum cleaner is powerful and its metal finishing may suggest that it is a robust apparatus. These experiential aspects play a role, for example, in the Kansei engineering approach to design [e.g., 5]. Because all sensory inputs can affect the way in which users perceive, make sense of, experience, and evaluate a product, several authors have proposed a multisensory approach to product design. In this approach, all perceptual impressions elicited when a potential user interacts with the product are explicitly created and evaluated [e.g., 6; 7; 8].

During the interactions with a product, users need to integrate all different types of sensory information in order to perceive the product as a whole. Nonetheless, some sensory information can have a larger effect on how a

product is experienced than other. If we can determine how important people find a specific type of sensory input, this may help product developers and designers to set priorities in allocating time and effort during product optimization. We define 'sensory importance' as the relative contribution of each sensory modality to the product experience. The dominant sensory modality is the modality that has the largest effect on the specific product experience.

A general and popular belief seems to be that vision is the dominant sensory modality. When people are asked which sensory modality they would miss most if they lost it, the majority is likely to indicate vision [9; 10]. Nonetheless, several anthropological studies have suggested that vision is not necessarily the dominant modality in all societies. In several non-Western societies taste, olfaction, or audition play dominant roles in important rituals [11]. In addition, there are indications that smell, taste, and touch used to be more important in Western societies several hundreds of years ago [12; 13] and that these societies have become more vision-oriented over the course of time. Possibly, the visual system is regarded dominant, because it plays a significant role in many contemporary, daily activities. The importance of vision may have increased over the years due to the products that were created, such as books, television, and computers that require major input from the visual modality. Alternatively, one could hypothesize that people report vision to be dominant, because people tend to be more aware of what they see than of what they hear, smell, feel, and taste [14].

The relative importance of a modality may depend on various aspects, such as the availability of sources of sensory stimulation, the degree of variation in sensory stimulation over various products, the usefulness of the sensory information during functional use, the proportion of time a modality is used actively, and the role of the stimulation in enjoying the product. Hence, the roles of the modalities depend not only on whether a certain type of sensory information is present, but also on whether the information is perceived, how it is processed, and how people react to it emotionally.

Apparently, the presence of particular products may influence the perceived relative importance of the senses. Therefore, we studied the importance of the sensory modalities for several different types of products. In the first group of studies we used a questionnaire approach, implying that we asked participants to reflect on their past experiences with particular products, and to indicate how important they thought the different senses were in their experiences with these products. In the second group of studies we used an experimental approach in which we created a number of product variants. In these studies, the experimental design allowed us to quantify the contribution of specific sensory inputs to the overall product experience.

2. Questionnaire studies

A questionnaire study in which participants reported the importance of the sensory modalities during the usage of 45 different products [10] demonstrated that on average the relative importance sequence of sensory modalities is vision, followed by touch, smell, audition and taste. In addition, when people were asked to indicate how important they found the different modalities in their lives in general, most of them selected vision as the most important modality. However, the importance ratings for the sensory modalities differed greatly between products. For almost half of the 45 products, the importance of vision was rated lower than one of the other

modalities. For example, audition is the most important modality for a washing machine and a coffee maker, which can be explained by the role of the sound in signaling the different stages of the process of washing or making coffee. Touch is most important for a computer mouse and a pen, and probably for any other hand tools as well. Smell plays a dominant role for a deodorant and (together with taste) for food products.

In addition, Schifferstein [10] investigated the roles of the modalities for three different types of product evaluations: product safety, ease of use, and product enjoyment. These three evaluations reflected three different aspects of product usage with relevance for almost any product. On average, he found the highest sensory importance ratings for enjoyment, lower for ease of use, and lowest for safety. Judgments of safety and ease of use are likely to depend more on product knowledge and on information provided on the product package and in instruction manuals than judgments of product enjoyment. Therefore, the role of the modalities will be larger in the latter case. Nevertheless, the role of the modalities in the various types of judgments mainly depended on the product.

Fenko et al. [15] addressed how sensory dominance changes over time. They investigated which sensory modalities contributed most to different stages of product experiences: during product purchase, after 1 week of usage, after 1 month, and 1 year. When consumers buy a product they are likely to pay attention primarily to its visual attributes, simply because other options to explore most products in a store are limited. But with time, other modalities can become more important. No matter how nice new shoes look, during usage it becomes more important whether they are comfortable or not; kitchen tools can be too heavy to use; an iron can produce a bad smell when used; new linen may not be as soft as the old, and so on.

Figure.1 Changes in modality dominance over time (Reprinted from Fenko et al., 2010 [15] with permission from Elsevier).

This is indeed what the results of the study showed. At the time of buying, the importance of vision was higher than the importance of all the other modalities (see Figure 1). Touch occupied the second position. Audition, smell and taste all played a very small role at the time of buying. This seems to be mainly determined by the limitations people experience when buying products in stores: products can only be observed from a distance, packages are closed, and many products cannot be tried. However, after the first week of usage, the importance of vision has decreased and the importance hierarchy seems to be determined by the importance of the various modalities for the product’s primary function. Nevertheless, the importance of the visual experience increases again during the first year of usage, because the product becomes old, dirty, and scratchy or it may become outdated due to fashion changes.

3. Experimental studies

Although it is very simple to ask persons directly to rate their importance of the various modalities, these introspective self-reports can only reflect what people are aware of. They do not necessarily reflect the impact that the different senses have on the overall product experience [e.g., 16; 17]. Especially for the 'lower' senses olfaction and gustation, which are almost never in the centre of attention, their importance may be underestimated [14]. By using an experimental approach, we will not need to ask participants to estimate the importance they attach to various sensory aspects. We can create product prototypes in which stimuli impinging on four different sensory modalities are integrated, and we calculate their relative importances from their impact on overall product evaluations. By using product prototypes we ensure that the results are applicable to real-life, multi-sensory product evaluation processes and are relevant for product design.

Our research approach is based on an additive model of sensory integration. According to the additive model, the participant’s evaluation of a combination of stimuli (i.e., a product) equals the sum of the (weighted) subjective values of the given stimuli:

$$r_{VTAO} = w_V s_V + w_T s_T + w_A s_A + w_O s_O$$

where r_{VTAO} stands for the response to the multisensory product, and s stands for the subjective value of the visual (V), tactual (T), auditory (A), and olfactory (O) stimuli, respectively. We investigate whether this approach can be used to assess the relative importance weights (w) of the sensory modalities for product experiences. The additive model assumes that the subjective value of each stimulus is independent of the other stimuli it is combined with. The additive model has proven to be successful in many areas of psychology, including sensory perception and attitude formation [see 18; 19] and the prediction of consumer preferences [e.g., 20; 21; 22].

The design of each study contains the following steps. In a pre-study, participants rate unisensory visual, tactual, auditory, or olfactory stimuli on a rating scale for a specific target experience dimension (e.g., pleasantness, freshness, noisiness). Subsequently, for each sensory dimension we select one stimulus pair that differs approximately to the same extent on this target dimension. In the main study, these stimuli are combined in all

possible combinations, yielding a set of multisensory products, which are then evaluated by a new group of participants.

3.1. Experimental studies on pleasantness

The first studies focused on the assessment of product pleasantness [23], represented by the items agreeable-disagreeable, pleasant-unpleasant, and good-bad. We decided to focus on this experience dimension, because these three items were shown to be related to all four sensory modalities (vision, audition, touch, olfaction) to the same degree [24; 25]. Product variants were created that varied in pleasantness for all these four sensory dimensions. Tests were performed for a portable air purifier and for a table lamp.

Unfortunately, in all studies the variation in scores on the pleasantness scale between the product variants was small, indicating that the effects of the manipulations were small and, in most cases, not statistically significant. Both studies only found a convincing systematic effect of product appearance (color differences) on the pleasantness scale. In contrast, participants' self-reported importances for the different modalities showed very different rank orders between studies.

We concluded that a possibly important aspect that is ignored by the proposed approach is that interactions may occur between the sensory stimulus attributes, whereas an additive model assumes no interaction effects. Especially in judgments of pleasantness for complex stimuli, the extent to which individual stimuli fit together or are congruent is important for the overall pleasantness judgment [e.g., 26; 27]. Despite these disappointing findings, the additive model may work very well in predicting sensory integration for other dimensions of product experience, as we will show below.

3.2. Experimental studies on freshness

In the studies on freshness [28], we created soft drinks, dishwashing liquids, and scented candles using fresh and non-fresh stimuli (colors and smells) in four different combinations. The results demonstrated that smell dominated the judgments of freshness for soft drinks and dishwashing liquids (see Figure 2). However, for scented candles smell and color were equally important in determining freshness. This suggests that the dominant sensory modality for the product experience of freshness depends on the characteristics of the particular product. In candles, for which freshness is not a necessary property, vision and smell both contribute to the degree of freshness. On the other hand, for products such as soft drinks and dishwashing liquids, where freshness is related to their main function, the experience of freshness mainly depends on the olfactory properties of the product.

Figure 2. Freshness ratings for soft drinks combining a fresh or non-fresh color (C_F or C_{NF}) with a fresh or non-fresh smell (S_F or S_{NF}) (Reprinted from Fenko et al., 2009 [28] with permission from Elsevier).

3.3. Experimental studies on warmth

In studies on perceived warmth [29], we designed products for which warmth is an important product attribute (scarves and breakfast trays), using different colors (vision) and materials (touch). The results demonstrated that both color and material contribute equally to the judgments of warmth in both products. A follow-up interview study distinguished between the literal and figurative meanings of warmth. The literal meaning is related to physical warmth and comfort, whereas the figurative meaning is associated with social interaction, intimacy and friendly atmosphere. The figurative meaning was mentioned more often in association with products than the literal meaning.

3.4. Experimental studies on noisiness

In studies on noisiness [30], we manipulated the auditory and visual properties of alarm clocks and whistle kettles. The results for both products suggest that noisiness evaluations were dominated by the products' sounds. The noisiness ratings were highly correlated with ratings of perceived annoyance. Results obtained using various synonyms of noisiness suggested that the experimental outcomes may differ quite substantially between these synonyms. This suggests that the exact wording used for the target experience may be crucial for the outcomes of the study.

4. Role of language and culture

Culture may play a role in determining the importance of a sensory modality. Language is one of the core components of any culture. It is central to communication and closely related to thought. Much of human cultural heritage is encapsulated in semantic concepts packed into words [31]. A proposal of linguistic relativity emphasizes a distinctive role of language in interpreting experience and influencing thought [32]. Whorf [33]

proposed that the categories and distinctions of each language determine a way of perceiving, analyzing, and acting in the world.

McLuhan [34] believed that the nature of media by which people communicate affects the ratio of sensory involvement. For example, the alphabet stresses the sense of sight, which causes people to think in linear, objective terms. He argued that Europeans and North Americans live in the visual mode, while for native Africans and other non-literate societies the auditory modality is dominant. However, anthropological data suggest that significant diversity exists in sensory dominance among non-literal peoples. Classen [35] describes three non-literate societies that have three different dominant sensory modalities: temperature is the most important sensory property for the Tzotzil of Mexico, smell for the Ongee of the Little Andaman Island, and vision for the Desana of Columbia.

Language effects may depend on the type of adjectives used to describe product experience. Some aspects of product experience seem to be uniquely unimodal: hue can only be experienced by sight, tickle can only be felt by touch, and pitch can only be differentiated by audition. Nevertheless, people are able to extract information derived from one sensory modality and use it in another. In addition, sensory terms that describe physical properties of things (such as 'warm' and 'cold') also describe some psychological qualities. Human language partly operates through metaphors [e.g., 36], which often refer to sensory phenomena. Good ideas are described as 'brilliant' and pleasant dreams as 'sweet'. Because we do not rely on each of our five senses equally and use some sensory modalities more often than others, it makes sense that certain sensory modalities have greater frequency in linguistic representation [37; 38].

The relevance of language differences for product experience research became explicitly evident in a recent study in which we used one and the same questionnaire to evaluate several qualitatively very different experiences: interacting with a cup versus drinking a beverage from a cup [39]. Although all the ballot descriptors were identical, response patterns suggested that the interpretation and meaning of the various descriptors differed substantially between the experimental conditions. For example, when participants evaluate empty cups, perceived fragility may be related to the likelihood that the cup will be damaged through usage or will break when it falls on the floor. This can explain the high ratings we found for disposable cups that are easily damaged during use or can be easily torn apart, but also for glass and ceramic cups that can fall apart if they are dropped. The fragility of these cups is unlikely to change dramatically when tea is added. Nevertheless, the experimental results suggested that the experience of drinking out of a ceramic cup became significantly less fragile by filling it with hot tea. Possibly this has to do with the increased weight of the cup. By increasing the weight, the cup may appear more solid, because an empty cup that is heavier often also is more solid. Furthermore, a heavy cup may provide a better grip when it is held in the hand.

Our sweetness ratings suggested a case in which a sensory interpretation of an item is combined with a more metaphorical interpretation. When evaluating drinking from a cup, sweet ratings are likely to reflect the perceived sweet taste of the drinks. However, when evaluating cups, the differences in sweetness ratings between the empty cups might be due to their different (pinkish) colors, which may be evaluated as more or less sweet.

Therefore, the sweet ratings may reflect both a literal (sweet taste) and a figurative (sweet colors) interpretation of the term, induced by differences in experimental conditions.

Fenko et al. [25] performed a questionnaire study to find out which sensory modalities are dominant for different descriptors of product experiences. We assume that for sensory descriptors the corresponding modalities will be dominant, such as taste for 'sweet', touch for 'hard', and audition for 'loud'. If an adjective has both a literal and a figurative meaning, we expect the link with the modality corresponding to the literal meaning to be stronger, because this is the original meaning. Symbolic and affective descriptors of product experience are likely to be multisensory, but possibly one or more sensory modalities play a more dominant role in assessing how interesting, modern, or exciting people find a particular product.

When the meaning of a product is expressed in words, it may be interpreted differently in different languages. Most adjectives that describe product experiences have several meanings, and usually not all these meanings can be translated adequately to another language. For example, the English word 'fresh' has 16 different meanings [40], which can be roughly divided into two groups: 1) new, recent, newly made, recently arrived, retaining its original qualities, not deteriorated or changed by lapse of time; 2) pure, invigorating, refreshing, not stale, musty, or vapid. In the Dutch language two different words are used to indicate these two meanings in the case of food products (*vers* for the first meaning and *fris* for the second meaning). When a text is translated from English into Dutch, the translation of the word 'fresh' is likely to have a more restricted meaning and fewer associations in Dutch than in English. Therefore, we assume that some descriptors of product experience have different associations in different languages and may differ in the extent to which they are associated with particular sensory modalities.

To test this assumption, we conducted a study with two groups of respondents: native Dutch speakers and native Russian speakers. Respondents indicated to what extent different sensory modalities contributed to the evaluation of 34 product properties [25]. The list included sensory descriptors (such as warm, noisy, and sweet), affective descriptors (such as exciting and cute), and symbolic descriptors (such as modern, and luxurious). Respondents were asked to think of any relevant product and to answer the question: "To what extent do the following senses contribute to your evaluation of a product as...?" They assessed the importance of five sensory modalities on 5-point scales from 'not important' (1) to 'very important' (5).

Overall mean ratings of the 34 experiences showed that vision had the highest rating for 14 experiences, touch for 10 experiences, taste for 4, and audition and olfaction for 3 experiences each. The affective descriptors relied equally on all sensory modalities. The symbolic descriptors were also multisensory, but relied more on the visual modality. As predicted, sensory descriptors had the highest ratings for the corresponding sensory modalities (e.g., touch for 'warm').

For 24 out of 34 experiences, the effect of sensory modality depended on the participant's native language. For example, 'spicy' appeared to be mainly a gustatory experience for Dutch respondents (*kruidig*) and olfactory for the Russian sample (*ароматный*). Olfaction was dominant for 'stale' in the Dutch group (*muf*), but for Russians

‘stale’ (*старый*) was a visual experience. For Dutch respondents ‘pure’ (*puur*) was a gustatory experience, while for Russians (*строгий*) it was visual.

Table 1. Mean relevance ratings of modalities for several product experiences that showed cultural differences [adapted from 25].

Language		Modality				
English	Dutch/ Russian	Vision	Audition	Touch	Olfaction	Taste
Colorful	fleurig	4.7	1.7	1.9	3.7	2.1
	красочный	4.9	1.4	1.6	1.4	1.4
Clean	schoon	4.6	1.4	3.7	4.3	2.7
	чистый	4.8	2.0	3.9	3.5	2.6
Warm	warm	3.3	1.9	4.6	2.1	2.6
	теплый	2.3	1.3	4.6	2.0	3.5
Sharp	scherp	4.0	2.3	4.4	2.4	3.2
	острый	2.9	1.6	3.4	2.5	4.3
Hard	hard	3.8	3.0	4.7	1.3	1.9
	твердый	3.3	1.6	4.8	1.3	2.4
Rough	ruw	4.1	2.2	4.8	1.4	1.8
	грубый	4.1	3.1	4.3	1.9	2.5
Quiet	stil	2.6	4.9	2.1	1.2	1.2
	спокойный	4.1	4.3	3.1	2.4	1.8
Stale	muf	3.0	1.6	2.2	4.7	3.4
	старый	4.5	2.2	3.7	3.0	2.5
Spicy	kruidig	2.6	1.1	1.6	4.2	4.7
	ароматный	2.2	1.5	1.6	4.6	3.1
Mild	mild	2.6	1.8	2.4	3.5	4.4
	мягкий	3.4	2.1	4.8	1.8	2.6
Pure	puur	3.9	2.4	2.6	3.6	4.2
	строгий	3.9	2.8	2.4	1.7	1.8
Modern	modern	4.8	2.6	3.2	2.0	1.8
	современный	4.5	3.5	2.6	2.5	2.2
Exciting	opwindend	4.3	2.9	3.8	3.3	3.2
	волнующий	3.8	3.1	3.1	3.4	2.6
Cute	schattig	4.7	3.0	3.6	2.1	1.6
	изящный	4.8	2.8	3.5	2.3	2.7

A possible explanation for these results is that the semantic connotations for sensory adjectives differ considerably between the languages. For instance, the Dutch word *mild* showed the highest importance rating for taste (4.4), but the Russian equivalent *мягкий* was mostly tactile (4.8). Apparently, *mild* in Dutch is similar to ‘mild’ in English when applied to food: not sharp, strong, or hot in flavor, not pungent, while *мягкий* in Russian is more synonymous to ‘soft’ and refers mostly to tactile properties.

Because the interpretations of words vary among cultures and individuals, it is difficult to standardize verbal communication with research participants from different cultures. In addition, because it is difficult to obtain item equivalence in questionnaire instruments even with the most accurate translation and back translation, cross-cultural studies are hard to interpret [41]. Differences in the meanings of sensory adjectives also have implications for international product marketing. Advertisers who want to use the same slogans and product descriptions in countries with different languages, need to be aware of the polysemy of sensory adjectives and cross-cultural differences in their metaphorical meanings [42].

To avoid ambiguity in research and design projects due to language differences, it is important to supplement verbal communication with physical materials and products and with observations of user behavior in order to gain in-depth understanding of user-product interactions. In addition, to cross cultural gaps it may be necessary to submerge in a foreign culture for a certain time period.

5. Conclusions

The importance people attribute to a specific sensory modality during user-product interaction has been shown to depend mainly on the type of product and its utilitarian function. Additional factors of interest are the stage of ownership, the task at hand, and the type of product aspects involved. In addition, the user's culture and language affect which aspects are evaluated as important and how these aspects are evaluated. The latter differences make it difficult to extend research results over cultural and language barriers and to understand the roles the senses play in other cultures.

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